

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D5.3 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND STAKEHOLDERS' IMPLEMENTATION REPORT

Call and Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.3 – Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Implementation Report outlines the execution of the Engagement and Outreach (E&O) plan, building on the framework established in *Deliverable 5.1 – Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Engagement Plan* [1]. It presents the outcomes of communication and dissemination activities carried out throughout the project, highlighting key dissemination materials, such as the project website, platform features, social media initiatives, promotional events, and scientific publications.

The deliverable begins with an introduction (**Chapter 1**) explaining the background, objectives, structure, and synergies with other tasks and deliverables. It then summarises the communication and dissemination goals (**Chapter 2**), including a table of key performance indicators (KPIs) and their achieved results. A detailed account of the communication and dissemination outcomes follows (**Chapter 3**), covering internal communications, project identity, communication materials, the project website, the INTEGER platform, social media activities, newsletters, video clips, interviews, articles, press releases, scientific publications, and events.

Stakeholder analysis and engagement activities are also addressed (**Chapter 4**), focusing on both interregional efforts (as detailed in *Deliverable 5.2 – Stakeholder Liaison with Relevant Initiatives*) and regional events (outlined in *Deliverable 4.4 – Report on Coordination Actions with Key Related Initiatives*).

In **Chapter 5**, feedback from stakeholders is presented, gathered through qualitative and quantitative methods, including interviews and surveys.

The deliverable concludes (**Chapter 6**) with a summary of the project's achievements and some conclusions, while also providing recommendations for future initiatives in communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement, ensuring the continued relevance and impact of the project's outcomes (**Chapter 7**).

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
i2CAT	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA
URV	UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI
FURV	FUNDACIO URV
F6S	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED
HAM	BEHOERDE FUER ARBEIT, GESUNDHEIT, SOZIALES, FAMILIE UND INTEGRATION HAMBURG
UJ	UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI
KTP	KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO
SHINE	SHINE 2EUROPE LDA
AFE	AFEDEMY, ACADEMY ON AGE-FRIENDLY ENVIRONMENTS IN EUROPE BV
E&O plan	Engagement and outreach plan
3 H	Triple Helix
4 H	Fourth Helix
CC BY	Creative Commons-licensed research

Table 1 - Symbols, abbreviations, and acronyms

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living and wellbeing, INTEGER aimed to bring forward three important innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative European Union (EU) innovation ecosystems:

- The INTEGER 4 Helix Col-laboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the 'Col-laboratories',
- An EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory, a true network of networks' community with capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects, and
- A new professional profile, the 'col-laber' or 'col-laboratory manager' as a multiplying agent of change of these integrated innovation ecosystems.

The three INTEGER reinforcing innovations aimed to multiply capacities for the integration of social innovation in EU innovation ecosystems:

- Boost win-win games between business and social oriented innovations addressing common challenges.
- Transform co-creation dynamics into disruptive and tangible new products, services or competencies.
- Co-design jointly public innovation policies.
- Develop capacity building of the new generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and ecosystems' enablers, the 'col-labers', and
- Devise funding and investment mechanisms for social innovation start-ups and SMEs to develop and scale up game changing innovations.

'Col-laboratories' and 'col-labers' aim to embrace economic and social-driven innovation communities across the EU. INTEGER took a collaborative approach, connecting business-driven methods with social innovation tailored to identified needs. The goal was to accelerate transformative outcomes by fostering win-win collaborations, local synergies, and effective coordination of actions. This included improved governance, implementation, adoption, and long-term impact.

The INTEGER project ran for 2 years, from February 2023 to January 2025, and was organised into 5 work packages.

ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH, AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION (WP5) is a horizontal Work Package (WP) across the project lifetime, dedicated to support the overall aims of the project and mobilise and

Figure 1 - Figure 1 - Pert Diagram of INTEGER

engage key stakeholders in Europe and beyond.

The specific objectives were to:

- a. **Raise awareness** of all relevant stakeholders about project activities, as well as its assets and resources.
- b. **Create engagement** and secure participation in activities among key stakeholders through a variety of initiatives and events.
- c. **Secure participation** of the relevant stakeholders and target groups in integrating social innovation actors in European ecosystems.
- d. **Reach out and enhance** collaboration with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks for a better outreach and sustainable impact, and e) enable uptake of the project results.

This was essential for the impact of the project, and that is why the INTEGER Consortium was fully engaged to communicate the concept, the activities, and the project results to successfully raise public awareness and plan for the uptake of the results.

Inside this WP, the **Task 5.1 Communication and dissemination plan and activities** defined the communication and dissemination strategy and framework for the exploitation of the knowledge generated by the project.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Deliverable 5.3 - Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders' Implementation Report, provides a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken during the project. It also examines stakeholder engagement by detailing the number of stakeholders involved and assessing their levels of engagement through a Power-Interest Grid analysis.

Chapter 2 outlines the communication and dissemination goals, including a table of key performance indicators (KPIs) and their achieved results. **Chapter 3** provides a comprehensive account of the outcomes, detailing internal communications, project identity, communication materials, the project website, the INTEGER platform, social media activities, newsletters, video clips, interviews, articles, press releases, scientific publications, and events.

Chapter 4 focuses on stakeholder analysis and engagement activities, addressing both interregional efforts (as detailed in *Deliverable 5.2 – Stakeholder Liaison with Relevant Initiatives*) and regional events (outlined in *Deliverable 4.4 – Report on Coordination Actions with Key Related Initiatives*).

In **Chapter 5**, feedback from stakeholders is presented, gathered through qualitative and quantitative methods, including interviews and surveys.

The deliverable concludes (**Chapter 6**) with a summary of the project's achievements and some conclusions, while also providing recommendations for future initiatives in communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement, ensuring the continued relevance and impact of the project's outcomes (**Chapter 7**).

1.3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

The Work Package 5 - ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH, AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION is a transversal work package across the project lifetime, dedicated to support the overall aims of the project and mobilise and engage key stakeholders in Europe and beyond. Building on *Deliverable 5.1 - Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders' Engagement Plan* [1], which outlined the methods and tools for effective stakeholder engagement, *Deliverable 5.3 - Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders' Implementation Report* provides a comprehensive account of the communication and dissemination activities carried out. This report integrates insights and results from Work Packages 2, 3, 4, and 5.

The deliverable also includes an analysis of stakeholder engagement throughout the project, covering both regional activities within the innovation regions (Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg), as detailed in *Deliverable 4.4 – Report on Coordination Actions with Key Related Initiatives*, and interregional activities, as outlined in *Deliverable 5.2 – Stakeholder Liaison with Relevant Initiatives* (see Table 2).

Table 2 - WP's, tasks and deliverables related to D5.3

WP	Task	Deliverable
WP2 - LEARNING FOR 4H COL-LABORATORY CO-CREATION	Task 2.1 Establish digital co-creation environments (the digital platform) for Best Practices Exchange	D2.2 – Col-laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan
	Task 2.2 Reinforce inter-ecosystem 3H & 4H dynamics between social entrepreneurs and stakeholders in each innovation ecosystem.	
	Task 2.3 European-wide Col-laborathon organisation and implementation.	D2.4 – Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged
	Task 2.4 Col-laborathon results exploitation	
WP3 – REGIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS' AS COLLABORATORY TESTBEDS	Task 3.1 Co-creation digital arenas for capacity building among innovator actors in the three regions.	D3.1 - Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and Training Pills Delivery (I)
	Task 3.2 Organisation and implementation of one Col-laborathon in each region.	D3.2 - Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and Training Pills Delivery (II)

	<p>Task 3.3 Piloting the incubation and acceleration of selected social-digital project</p>	<p>D3.3 - Report on main features of the 3 regional Innovation Ecosystem Models. URV. M9</p> <p>D3.4 - Three Col-laborathons Final Reports with successful project shortlist and awardees</p>
<p>WP4 – INTEGER 4H MODEL & EU HEALTHY LIVING COL-LABORATORY DEPLOYMENT</p>	<p>Task 4.1 Gathering and systematisation of relevant information and material in the INTEGER platform hub.</p> <p>Task 4.2 Development of a comprehensive model to accelerate the integration and collaboration of social innovation actors and digital business entrepreneurial hubs.</p> <p>Task 4.3 Deployment and sustainability of the EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory.</p> <p>Task 4.4 Interconnecting and exchange with the related initiatives, networks, communities, and projects</p>	<p>D4.2 - EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted</p> <p>D4.3 – INTEGER 4H col-laboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications</p> <p>D4.4 - Report on coordination actions with key related initiatives</p>
<p>WP5 – ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION</p>	<p>Task 5.1 Communication and dissemination plan and activities.</p> <p>Task 5.2 Stakeholder engagement and liaison with relevant initiatives.</p> <p>Task 5.3 Impact monitoring and maximisation plan and activities</p>	<p>D5.1 - Communication, dissemination, and stakeholders' engagement plan</p> <p>D5.2 - Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives and impact monitoring report</p>

2. DISSEMINATION SUMMARY AND GOALS

The Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders' Engagement Strategy for INTEGER was initially defined as a preliminary approach during the proposal preparation, based on specific objectives designed to maximise the impact of the project both during and beyond the end of the funding period.

As planned, the project dissemination activities were targeted to create awareness and make available knowledge and results of the project to relevant stakeholders, but mostly to foster win-win games and citizen participation that CONNECT and ENGAGE 4H stakeholders in social innovation ecosystems.

The overall goal of this Strategy and Plan is to communicate the project concept and activities and promote INTEGER to successfully raise public awareness and plan for the uptake of the results. It aims to ensure wide exposure and promotion of the project results to targeted stakeholders and the media and facilitate their use beyond the project's lifetime.

The INTEGER Consortium engaged in implementing this broad strategy to boost the project outcomes and benefits, to reach the widest possible audience and to ensure the sustainability of the outputs developed in the project.

The following table explains the consortium idea for this strategy.

Figure 2 - Building and enlarging the INTEGER community

The dissemination and communication strategy were coordinated by SHINE and AFE and implemented collaboratively by the entire consortium.

As mentioned, to keep the strategy in line with the project development, the partners monitored and provided relevant adjustments when necessary. Additionally, the project was continuously open to new opportunities of dissemination and the plan was adapted and updated along the project and the associated activities redirected as new ideas and opportunities arise.

2.1 Communication and Dissemination Objectives

The overall objectives for INTEGER communication and dissemination activities were thought and described in the application as one of the project's impact points. The following table briefly describes these:

Table 3 - Communication & Dissemination Objectives and Impact

	Objectives	Impact
	Raise awareness of all relevant stakeholders about project activities, as well as its assets and resources.	Stakeholders are being kept informed about the work progress and the results during the work process and beyond.
	Create engagement and secure participation in activities among key stakeholders through a variety of initiatives and events	The wider public and relevant stakeholder groups, such as academia, researchers and policymakers are informed of INTEGER's achievements and materials and act as replicators of knowledge in their own communities.
	Secure participation of the relevant stakeholders and target groups in integrating social innovation actors in European ecosystems.	End-users and stakeholders are being made aware of the INTEGER tools and goals, which are promoted among the relevant stakeholders and their use towards the inclusion of end-users is encouraged.
	Reach out and enhance collaboration with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks.	Enable a sustainable impact and ensure exploration beyond the project period.

	Enable uptake of the project result.	Development of a result closer to what stakeholders need and guarantee of its application.
---	---	--

2.2 Communication & Dissemination KPIs

The specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of INTEGER communication and dissemination activities evolved as appropriate to each stage of the project. Two years after, the list of the KPIs is updated and displayed in the table below:

Table 4 - KPI's communication & dissemination

Target Audiences	Activity/channel	Indicator/KPI	Goal	End of project
All	INTEGER Social Media	Number of X (former Twitter) followers	300	441 ¹
		Number of LinkedIn followers	300	441
		Number of articles featured in influencing Twitter handles	10	13 ²
All	Local/regional/national press	Number of articles	10	12
RTO & universities, health & care, tech & service providers, industry	Scientific publications	Number of papers accepted on international relevant journals	2	5
	Non-scientific publications	Number of articles and interviews on online magazines, specialised portals and platforms	6	8
	Participation in conferences, exhibitions, virtual or F2F	Number of presentations/keynote speeches/panels/workshops featured in the programme	10	40

¹ The former Twitter platform (now X) proved to be an ineffective social media platform for INTEGER project, given that several partners lacked accounts. In response, the SHINE team shifted its focus to the project's LinkedIn account. They increased the frequency of posts on LinkedIn, ensuring greater engagement and expanding the follower base on this platform. As a result, the reported follower numbers reflect those on LinkedIn.

² Similarly to the above, this refers to the number of LinkedIn articles posted by individuals or companies that mention or discuss the INTEGER project.

		of national and international conferences and events organised by other networks, multipliers, programmes and initiatives		
All	Newsletters	Number of newsletter releases to the contacts included in the partners' mailing list + new subscribers reached via social media campaigning	6	6
All	Graphic materials	Number of infographic and visuals	20	23
		Number of leaflets distributed (2 versions: one preliminary focusing on goals and channels and an intermediate with spotlights on tools – English + pilots' languages)	1000	>1200
		Project official roll-up and poster	1	1

In Year 1, the key focus was on creating awareness of the INTEGER project through communication activities and some dissemination in scientific networks. In Year 2 the focus was mainly on how to target more scientific dissemination, intensifying awareness and scientific publications and promoting exploitation of INTEGER outputs and their further upscale and broader use.

The following subsections provide a detailed overview of the achievements in communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement throughout the project.

3. COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION RESULTS

The Consortium made use of several channels and activities to communicate and/or disseminate INTEGER at local, regional, national and international levels, as outlined in *Deliverable 5.1* [1].

The following sections are an overview of the achievements in internal communications, the development of a project identity, communication materials and templates, the project website, the INTEGER platform, and social media efforts. Specific activities also included updates and content shared on partner websites and social media channels, as well as the creation of newsletters, videopills, interviews, articles, zoom articles, press releases, and scientific and conference publications. Additionally, an analysis of the events, conferences, webinars, and other dissemination opportunities are provided to assess the Consortium's efforts in ensuring broad impact and engagement.

3.1 Internal communications

INTEGER partners used a mixture of emails and networking tools to manage internal communication and information exchanges within the Consortium as follows, namely:

- Sharing documents, design and development activities – Google Drive and emails
- Communication between partners - Glocal.network
- Online meetings – Google Meet

The project coordination was done through the developed section in the glocal.network platform. Each WP has a specific space for partners to interact and upload all information so that the project progress is easily traceable. In some instances, communications and invitations were not received by certain consortium members. Despite collaborating with the platform owners, the cause of this issue could not be identified. As a result, it was decided to use more "standard tools", such as email and calendar invitations, for future events and communications.

3.2 Project Identity

The basis of the project identity consists of a logo, developed by SHINE and supported by a palette of colours and fonts.

INTEGER

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ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

Figure 3 - INTEGER logo

To guide the partners and provide a coherent image in all materials and communication, SHINE developed an INTEGER Visual Identity Manual. The [Manual](#) is available in Google Drive shared folder and provides the necessary information on the correct use of the logo, their variations and colour pallet.

Figure 4 - INTEGER visual identity manual

3.3 Communication materials and templates

INTEGER has created standard templates to be used by the Consortium partners to promote consistency and coherence in branding and communications. These include:

- [Word templates](#) – general document and template for project deliverables.

The figure displays a grid of 12 pages from the INTEGER word template, arranged in three rows and four columns. Each page features the INTEGER logo and the text 'D5.3 NAME OF THE DELIVERABLE' in the top right corner. The pages are as follows:

- Page 1 (Top Left):** Cover page with the INTEGER logo, 'INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS', 'DELIVERABLE TITLE', 'Call and Topic: HORIZON-ER-2022-CONNECT-01-02', 'Version 0.0 | xx.xx.xxxx', and 'Funded by the European Union'.
- Page 2 (Top Middle-Left):** 'DOCUMENT INFORMATION' section with a table for document details and a 'DOCUMENT HISTORY' table.
- Page 3 (Top Middle-Right):** 'Copyright message' section with a text box containing copyright information.
- Page 4 (Middle Left):** 'EXECUTIVE SUMMARY' section.
- Page 5 (Middle Middle-Left):** 'TABLE OF CONTENTS' section with 'LIST OF FIGURES' and 'LIST OF TABLES'.
- Page 6 (Middle Middle-Right):** 'SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS' section with a table listing symbols and their descriptions.
- Page 7 (Bottom Left):** '1 INTRODUCTION' section with sub-sections 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and 1.4.
- Page 8 (Bottom Middle-Left):** 'REFERENCES' section.
- Page 9 (Bottom Middle-Right):** '3 CONCLUSIONS' section.

Figure 5 - INTEGER word template

- [Powerpoint template](#) for project presentations:

Figure 6 - INTEGER power point template

- [Word template for meetings agenda and minutes:](#)

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

<Project Management Meeting / Monthly Meeting / Other name>	
DATE	<DD Month YYYY> -<HH:mm am/pm CET>
LINK	Meeting link
PROJECT	INTEGER Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions

OBJECTIVES OF THE MEETING

- Objective

AGENDA

ATTENDEES

- XX

OPEN ACTION POINTS
(Includes list of action points of previous meetings and this meeting)

DATE	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION

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MEETING REPORT/MINUTES

1. WPX | Title of the work-package

- [Agenda point 1 \(responsible partner\)](#)

Summary of the discussion.

ACTION POINTS:

2. WPX | Title of the work-package

- [Agenda point 2 \(responsible partner\)](#)

Summary of the discussion.

ACTION POINTS:

APPROVED ON/BY: XX

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Figure 7 - INTEGER word meeting template

To support the project's online dissemination through the website, social media, targeted communication with key stakeholders, and event participation, other materials were developed: **two leaflets** (the first focusing on project goals and dissemination channels, and the final - agreed upon by partners - highlighting the 4H Model to draw attention to project outcomes). The leaflets have been distributed digitally through the networks of consortium partners and on social media, ensuring a more sustainable approach. To maximise outreach, the leaflet was included in newsletters, reaching at least 1200 contacts.

The image shows a digital mockup of the INTEGER first leaflet. It features the INTEGER logo at the top left, followed by a photograph of a group of people in a meeting. The main title is "CREATING COL-LABORATORIES FOR IMPROVED BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES OF SOCIAL INNOVATION". Below this, there are sections for "WHY?", "WHAT?", "COL-LABORATHONS", and "INTEGER 4H MODEL". The "4H MODEL" section includes a circular diagram with four quadrants: Governance, Multi-facilitation, Implementation, and Integration of needs, visions, interests & policy goals. At the bottom, there is a large diagram titled "INTEGRATING 3H AND 4H MODELS FOR A EUROPEAN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS TRANSITION" which maps various innovation ecosystems and digital technologies. The leaflet also includes contact information, social media links, and logos of partners and the European Union.

Figure 8 - INTEGER first leaflet

The image shows two promotional materials for the INTEGER project. On the left is a second leaflet titled 'INTEGER 4H MODEL'. It features a central diagram with '4H' in the middle, surrounded by icons for Sustainability, Belonging, Management, Evaluation, Financing, and Collaboration. Text sections include 'WHAT IS IT?', 'WHY IS IT IMPORTANT?', and 'HOW CAN IT BE USED?'. On the right is a poster titled 'INTEGRATING 3H AND 4H MODELS FOR A EUROPEAN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS TRANSITION'. It features a central 'INTEGER' logo and lists various innovation models like National Innovation Ecosystems, Living Labs, and Digital Technologies and Networks. Both materials include social media links and partner logos.

Figure 9 - INTEGER second leaflet (left) and poster (right)

A poster and a roll-up banner have been designed to promote INTEGER at relevant conferences and meetings, enhancing visibility and dissemination efforts.

The image shows a roll-up banner for the INTEGER project. It features the INTEGER logo at the top, followed by the project's mission statement: 'INTEGER aims to bring together actors from 3H and 4H systems to face common challenges: the "col-laboratories", a next generation of living labs, a cooperative instrument based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven economic innovation and social-driven innovation.' Below this is a photograph of a group of people sitting around a table, engaged in a discussion. At the bottom, there are social media links and partner logos.

Figure 10 - The INTEGER roll-up on the right and in use during a project presentation on the left

Regarding the total number of infographics and visuals, the following Table 5 lists all those achieved, which in total is 23:

Table 5 – List of INTEGER infographics and visuals

Infographics and visuals	
1	INTEGER logo
2	INTEGER visual identity manual
3	Leaflet 1
4	Leaflet 2
5	INTEGER deliverable template
6	INTEGER meeting minutes
7	INTEGER one page template
8	INTEGER presentation template
9	Newsletter template (x6)
10	Infographic “Integrating 3H and 4H models for a European Innovation Ecosystem Transition”
11	Infographic map “Who we are”
12	Learning network cover
13	Webinar poster
14	Communicate, impact, transform: the im-perfect pitch - poster
15	How to sell with AI and LinkedIn - poster
16	Col.laber training poster
17	Infographic “Where we are”
18	Learning network launch
19	Digital award finalist and first prize (page 55)
20	Videos design (x27)
21	“Towards the social innovation lighthouse” design
22	Interviews template (x5)
23	Zoom articles template (x6)

3.4 Website

The INTEGER website (<https://integercollab.eu/>) has served as the central hub for all project updates, providing access to the INTEGER platform ([Glocal.platform](#)), and showcasing the project's aims, objectives, and team.

Figure 11 - INTEGER Website (Home)

The website has been regularly updated with project news and newsletters in the “What’s New” section, featuring a total of 66 news articles.

Figure 12 - INTEGER Website: “What’s New” Section

The project's outputs are available in the “Resources” section, which includes the **press kit** (containing the logo, visual identity manual, poster, roll-up, two leaflets), audio and video pills, **project reports** (deliverables), and various **articles**. These articles include those published prior to the INTEGER project and related to it as well as content produced during the project, such as Zoom-specific issues, LinkedIn articles, and interviews with key stakeholders. Additionally, another section features **policy papers** collected to support the development of project-related policy recommendations, with a focus on health and well-being in the context of digital

advancements. The section concludes with links to the **EU Col-laboratory** membership form and the Terms of Reference (ToR).

Figure 13 - Figure 13 - INTEGER Website: "Resources" Section

The website tracks analytics on visitor numbers and overall activity, enabling continuous analysis and data-driven improvements to the Communication Plan for more effective outreach. The INTEGER website has attracted **31,738 unique visitors**, with monthly fluctuations as illustrated in Figure 14. The peak in unique visitors occurred in May 2024, while the highest number of pageviews was recorded in June 2023. Visitors originated from various countries, including the United Kingdom, Portugal, Spain, Poland, Germany, Greece, and Serbia, among others with fewer pageviews, as depicted in the map in Figure 15.

Figure 14 - Monthly visits to the INTEGER website

Figure 15 - Website statistics by country, showcasing user engagement and geographic reach of the INTEGER website

3.5 INTEGER

To gather everything in one place, that allows stakeholders of INTEGER project to interact and also with project management tools, a platform has been developed (for detailed details consult *Deliverable 2.3 - Platform Guidelines* and made it accessible on [INTEGER pill 2: How to use theglocal.network](#)). The INTEGER platform ([theglocalnetwork](#)) has been regularly updated with fresh content, not only from the INTEGER project but also from relevant opportunities and dissemination activities, such as available funding, open calls and conferences. This approach aimed to establish the platform as a valuable resource where participants can access essential knowledge to apply in their professional practices. In addition to engaging **203 participants**, a total of **102 posts** have been published.

Figure 16 - "Discover" section in INTEGER platform

Moreover, within the platform, the "**Participate**" section includes a dedicated "[Col-labers' and Facilitators' Corner](#)", where Col-labers and facilitators can connect through discussions, shared content, and explore their roles and responsibilities. This section features videos on the INTEGER project, Col-labers, and training, as well as recordings from the Col-labers Training Day and one of the incubation training sessions.

Additionally, the [INTEGER Learning Network](#) has been established as a central hub for sharing research, exploring new opportunities, and discovering digital solutions in the field of social innovation related to health and well-being across Europe and beyond. Training materials are also accessible, including those from the INTEGER project (such as mentorship session canvases and other resources), as well as tools for social innovation and facilitation. Moreover, materials from other projects in the same call as INTEGER, shared with the team, are also available.

Figure 17 - Learning network on the INTEGER platform

Despite these efforts, engagement on the platform remained limited. This was evident from inconsistent collaboration within the online groups and the lack of participation in other sections of the platform. Given that the licence for [theglobal.network](#) will expire in the coming months and the associated costs cannot be sustained due to the low number of users, a decision has been made to transfer to another platform, [Decidim](#).

The choice of Decidim comes from its open-source nature and the fact that “hundreds of organisations around the world trust Decidim for their democratic processes” [2], which aligns closely with INTEGER’s vision. This transition aims to ensure the sustainability of INTEGER’s results and keep the network active, starting from February 1, 2025.

To facilitate this transfer, a document outlining a [step-by-step registration](#) process has been shared, both on the platform [here](#), on the INTEGER website [here](#) and through the EU Colaboratory members.

3.6 Social Media

Social networks play an important role in getting the public interested in the INTEGER project, so that public participation is maximised as much as possible.

Social media has been essential in generating public interest and maximizing participation in the INTEGER project. Dedicated LinkedIn and X (former Twitter) accounts were created to share project updates and announcements through concise and appropriate messages. However, as previously noted, X (former Twitter) proved less effective due to many partners lacking active accounts. In response, the team strategically shifted focus to LinkedIn, increasing posting frequency to boost engagement and grow the project's follower base.

Figure 18 - INTEGER LinkedIn account

All partners were involved in this task. To facilitate their participation, SHINE disseminated guidelines ([here](#)) providing insights on creating appealing social media posts. Additionally, a calendar was created to ensure equal involvement of all partners in the posting schedule (see Figure 19 – Communication calendar on social media).

Communication Calendar - Posts on LinkedIn INTEGER account											
Weeks	nov/23	dez/23									
Week 1		F6S									
Week 2		HAM									
Week 3	I2CAT	UJK									
Week 4	URV	KTP									
Weeks	fev/24	mar/24	abr/24	mai/24	jun/24	jul/24	ago/24	set/24	out/24	nov/24	dez/24
Week 1	F6S	SHINE	F6S								
Week 2	HAM	AFE	HAM								
Week 3	UJK	I2CAT	UJK								
Week 4	KTP	URV	KTP								

Figure 19 – Communication calendar on social media

LinkedIn was actively used to share updates and outputs from the INTEGER project, highlight news from other projects with which INTEGER has built synergies or connections, and post or repost articles related to topics aligned with the project's focus.

Figure 20 - Examples of posts about INTEGER in social media

This effort resulted in **60** original LinkedIn posts, **16** reposts, and a total of **441** followers. Additionally, INTEGER was mentioned in **14** posts by other organisations and stakeholders.

3.7 Partner website and social media

The consortium partners actively promoted the INTEGER project within their own audiences and networks by featuring it on their organisations' websites. Examples of these can be found below.

Figure 21 - SHINE 2Europe web site print – INTEGER on partner website

Figure 22 – i2CAT web site print – INTEGER on partner website

3.8 Newsletters

INTEGER newsletters developed and circulated to all those registering their interest on the project website.

In addition, the Consortium partners use their networks, adhering to GDPR guidelines, to garner and raise interest in the project, to increase the number of stakeholders registering their interest in the project and the size of the overall INTEGER mailing list.

The newsletter has been designed using the visual identity manual and issued periodically (6 in total over the project lifetime).

Table 6 – List of newsletters

Newsletter	Month	Year	Content
1 [access here]	May	2023	Dissemination of: Kick-off meeting and of the 3 ecosystem visits with details. Announcement of the pre-event (what is the event and what are the objectives?, when and where will take place, to whom?, who is going to organise it?) and the website and social media launch.
2 [access here]	September	2023	Dissemination of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory, the article between INTEGER and a project sister (SIRENE), the attendance of partners at various events, video and training pills. Announcement of channels through which individuals or organizations can contact INTEGER (including its platform).
3 [access here]	March	2024	Special emphasis was placed on the platform, along with announcements and dissemination of the Col-laber training to attract more participants. Dissemination of insights from the General Assembly, conferences attended by partners. Sharing of the three Col-laborathons held in the innovation ecosystems of Hamburg, Catalonia, and Krakow, as well as the INTEGER Col-laborathon Grand Finale. Col-laber videopills were also distributed.

<p>4 [access here]</p>	<p>July</p>	<p>2024</p>	<p>Dissemination efforts focused on promoting participation in the Glocal Platform by highlighting its community benefits and collaboration opportunities. Key announcements featured the upcoming webinar, the release of the INTEGER 4H Model, and the launch of the Learning Network. Additionally, recent activities were shared, including the Col-laber Training, the second edition of the AHathon in Krakow, two online sessions from the incubation training, the presentation of outcomes from INTEGER's session at the European Week of Regions and Cities, and participation in various conferences.</p>
<p>5 [access here]</p>	<p>December</p>	<p>2024</p>	<p>Presentation of INTEGER training pills and Col-laber pills, along with guidance on how to join the Learning Network. Recent activities were also shared, including the Final General Assembly, mentorship sessions, and outcomes from the webinar. Additionally, updates covered consortium partner meetings aimed at fostering synergies with other projects, as well as the presentation of INTEGER at a conference and another international event.</p>
<p>6 [access here]</p>	<p>January</p>	<p>2025</p>	<p>The final newsletter is a wrap-up including all key achievements and deliverables from INTEGER, such as Zoom articles, LinkedIn articles, the 4H Model, Col-laborathons, and the Col-laber role, among others. It also highlights INTEGER's presence at three major conferences and provides clear instructions on how to access and utilise the new INTEGER platform.</p>

3.9 Video pills

A total of **27 videos** were developed for various purposes and targeted at different audiences. These materials were disseminated across five key channels: the [TheGlocal.Network](#) - INTEGER platform, the [INTEGER project website](#) (under “Resources” and “Audio and videopills” section), the [Youtube INTEGER channel](#), the [INTEGER LinkedIn](#) social network.

Led by SHINE, **10 videos** were produced to introduce project partners and present the project’s aims and objectives, exceeding the 8 initially proposed. The full list of videos is below:

Table 7 – List of INTEGER videos presenting the project and consortium partners

Videos	
1	Meet the partner i2CAT Foundation
2	Meet the partner Universat Rovira i Virgili
3	Meet the partner F6S
4	Meet the partner Behörde für Arbeit, Soziales, Familie und Integration Hamburg
5	Meet the partner Uniwersyteit Jagiellonski
6	Meet the partner Krakow Technology Park
7	Meet the partner SHINE 2Europe
8	Meet the partner AFEdemy
9	WHY INTEGER?
10	Why is this project so relevant?

MEET THE PARTNERS

To support the scaling and replication of the project across other EU regions, **13 video pills** were developed under AFE's leadership. The topics for these short videos were carefully planned within Deliverables 3.1 [3] and 3.2 [4], following a structured concept for thematic distribution. These videos include **INTEGER Pills** (2) describing the project and its goals, **Col-laber Pills** (5) showcasing the evolving role of the Col-laber as a networking actor in innovation ecosystems, and **Training Pills** (6) featuring expert insights on relevant topics and practical information related to the INTEGER project and broader EU challenges. In total, 8 videos with experts were produced, surpassing the 5 initially planned in the proposal. The full list of videos is provided below.

Table 8 - List of List of INTEGER video pills, Col-laber pills and Training pills

Videos	Name of expert and affiliation
INTEGER Pills	
1 INTEGER pill 1: The INTEGER project	<i>Toni Caro – i2CAT (INTEGER consortium)</i>
2 INTEGER pill 2: How to use theglobal.network	--
Col.laber Pills	
3 Col.laber pill 1: The Col-laber and its role as facilitator	Theda Minthe – Head of Strategy and Policy Department, City of Hannover)
4 Col.laber pill 2: How to do offline and online facilitation as a Col-laber	--
5 Col.laber pill 3: Skills of a Col-laber	--
6 Col.laber pill 4: Co-creation in Social Innovation	--
7 Col.laber pill 5: How to keep your digital community engaged and boost your initiative	--
Training Pills	
8 Training pill 1: What is Social Innovation	Karin Stiehr – Institute for Social Infrastructure
9 Training pill 2: How the public sector can foster social and business driven win win games	<i>Kai Schnackenberg - Behörde für Arbeit, Soziales, Familie und Integration Hamburg (INTEGER consortium)</i>
10 Training pill 3: Role and benefits of the academia in social innovation ecosystems	Krzysztof Gurba - Deputy Director of Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU (Jagiellonian University)
11 Training pill 4: Role and benefits of the industry in social innovation ecosystems	Arkadiusz Tomasiak – Member of the Board, Fundacja Brata Alberta
12 Training pill 5: Which investment types can contribute to a higher social impact	--

13	Training pill 6: How to create a successful dissemination strategy	Mara Diaconu - TechInnovator PhD Candidate Sustainable Innovation Norwegian University of Science and Technology
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INTEGER PILLS

COL.LABER PILL

TRAINING PILL

Figure 23 – Screenshot of video pills from the "Audio and Video Pills" Section on the INTEGER website

Additionally, there are **4 videos featuring interviews** with three experts and another with two mentees from the Catalonian ecosystem.

Table 9 - List of INTEGER video interviews

Videos		Name of expert and affiliation
1	What are the barriers and how can INTEGER help?	Maria Wojtacha – Director of the Foundation Internationaler Bund Polska
2	Bridging technology and physical health	Lena Reisloh – ASPCAT (Agencia de Salut Publica de Catalunya)
3	Which gaps does INTEGER address?	Marylyn M. Addo – Professor and Director, Institute for Infection Research and Vaccine Development (Hamburg)
4	INTEGER Mentorship sessions	Albert Munne – memima baby Rosina Malagrida - Living Lab for Health Research

3.10 Interviews

A total of **15 interviews** (out of the 13 suggested in the proposal) have been conducted with participants of INTEGER activities in two formats: video and written. The video interviews highlight 8 experts and 2 mentees - previously mentioned - strategically aligned with the Col-laber and Training Pills to maximise relevance and impact. Additionally, written interviews were carried out with mentees participating in mentorship sessions across the regional innovation ecosystems of Hamburg, Catalonia, and Krakow. Furthermore, one expert from the INTEGER consortium were interviewed to share their insights and perspectives as mentor.

Below is a table summarising the interviews, their formats, and links to the respective recordings and transcripts.

Table 10 - List of interviews and their respective format

	Name of interviewee and affiliation	Format / Link
1	Theda Minthe – Head of Strategy and Policy Department, City of Hannover)	Video / Col.laber pill 1: The Col-laber and its role as facilitator
2	Karin Stiehr – Institute for Social Infrastructure	Video / Training pill 1: What is Social Innovation
3	Krzysztof Gurba - Deputy Director of Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU (Jagiellonian University)	Video / Training pill 3: Role and benefits of the academia in social innovation ecosystems
4	Arkadiusz Tomasiak – Member of the Board, Fundacja Brata Alberta	Video / Training pill 4: Role and benefits of the industry in social innovation ecosystems
5	Mara Diaconu - TechInnovator PhD Candidate Sustainable Innovation Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Video / Training pill 6: How to create a successful dissemination strategy

6	Maria Wojtacha – Director of the Foundation Internationaler Bund Polska	Video / What are the barriers and how can INTEGER help?
7	Lena Reisloh – ASPCAT (Agencia de Salut Publica de Catalunya)	Video / Bridging technology and physical health
8	Marylyn M. Addo – Professor and Director, Institute for Infection Research and Vaccine Development (Hamburg)	Video / Which gaps does INTEGER address?
9	Albert Munne – memima baby	Video / INTEGER Mentorship sessions (Catalonia)
10	Rosina Malagrida - Living Lab for Health Research	Video / INTEGER Mentorship sessions (Catalonia)
11	Karina Simieli – SeniorLab	Written / Mentorship sessions (Catalonia)
12	Marta Rofin- Bax & Company	Written / Mentorship sessions (Catalonia)
13	Monika Bartkowicz - Drogowskazy	Written / Mentorship sessions (Krakow)
14	<i>Agnieszka Włodarczyk – Krakow Technology Park (INTEGER Consortium)</i>	Written / Mentorship sessions (Krakow)
16	Natalia Bialobrzewska – kontakt kolektiv	Written / Mentorship sessions (Hamburg)

3.11 Articles on online magazines, specialised portals and platforms

A total of **8 articles** have been produced, exceeding the 6 initially proposed, to disseminate updates and outcomes of the INTEGER project. These articles were published on the INTEGER LinkedIn account and the website of a sister project, aiming to provide the general public with a more in-depth understanding of the project's progress and results. The first three articles (see Table 11, below) were developed by the INTEGER consortium, while four additional articles were created in collaboration with sister projects - SIRENE, CHESS, POSITIVE, and Consolid8 - who participated in the INTEGER webinar (further details available in Deliverable 5.2). This collaboration aimed to reach a broader audience and enhance the dissemination of project outcomes.

Table 11 - List of INTEGER articles

Articles		Where they have been disseminated
1	Become part of the INTEGER EU Col·laboratory on Health and Wellbeing	LinkedIn articles
2	Driving Innovation Through Collaboration: Insights from INTEGER's Col·laborathons	LinkedIn articles
3	The role of Col·labers in Social Innovation	LinkedIn articles
4	INTEGER 4H Model	LinkedIn articles
5	Similarities and Differences: Exploring the sister projects CHESS and INTEGER	LinkedIn articles
6	Discover more about POSITIVE and INTEGER: Two sister projects	LinkedIn articles

7	Learn more about Consolid8 and INTEGER: Two sister projects	LinkedIn articles
8	IBESI & INTEGER	LinkedIn articles

3.12 Zoom articles

To simplify and effectively communicate some of the more complex concepts of the INTEGER project to a general audience, **6 Zoom-specific articles** were developed. The topics of these articles, listed in Table 12, have been shared across social media platforms and are featured in a dedicated "Zoom Articles" section within the "Articles" page on the project website (see Figure 24).

Table 12 - Topics and links to zoom-specific articles featured in the INTEGER project

Zoom-specific articles	
1	Social innovation
2	European Col-laborathory
3	Col.laber
4	INTEGER 4H Model
5	Col-laborathons
6	Mentorship sessions

Figure 24 - Screenshot of video pills from the "Audio and Video Pills" Section on the INTEGER website

3.13 Articles in local/regional/national/international press

The Consortium actively engages with the media through the distribution of press releases aimed at the general public, ensuring stakeholders are informed about the project's activities and results. A press release was issued in April 2023 in English and translated into all partner languages. Another was published after the Final General Assembly in November, which was also shared with all partners for adaptation to their respective languages and regional or

national contexts. Moreover, articles have been written and shared by organisations involved in the project, particularly through their formal engagement via the Terms of Reference, aiming to highlight and promote their collaboration with the INTEGER project.

Table 13 - List of articles in local / regional / national / international press

	Article title / Link	Country	Local / regional/ national /international press	Date
1	SAVE THE DATE: SIRENE project will be at the workshop "Projects under the European Innovation Ecosystems Work Programme in support of the New European Innovation Agenda" [INTEGER project is mentioned in the news]	NA	International	25/01/2023
2	i2CAT liderarà un projecte europeu de tecnologies digitals [i2CAT leads a European digital technologies project]	Spain	Regional	02/09/2023
3	Qⁿ Alliance strengthens ties with the European INTEGER project, focused on the generation of new models of Quadruple Helix Living Labs related to Health and Wellbeing	Spain	Regional	29/09/2023
4	VITALISE Joins the EU INTEGER Collaboratory at Open Living Lab Days	NA	International	16/10/2023
5	Celebrating a Milestone Moment: The EU INTEGER Collaboratory on Health and Wellbeing		International	31/10/2023
6	Eines i idees perquè els projectes socials siguin viables econòmicament [Tools and ideas to make social projects economically viable]	Spain	Regional	01/12/2023
7	Salut i benestar social: la quàdruple hèlix com a element disruptor [Health and social wellbeing: the quadruple helix with the disruptor element]	Spain	Regional	4/12/2023
8	O innowacjach, ale tym razem społecznych! [About innovation, but this time social innovation!]	Poland	Regional	5/12/2023
9	AHathon i TONA międzypokoleniowych pomysłów [AHathon and a TON of intergenerational ideas]	Poland	International	11/12/2023

10	Rozwiń kompetencje cyfrowe z zakresu innowacji społecznych! [Develop digital competence with social innovation!]	Poland	Regional	02/04/2024
11	Suara Cooperativa signs an agreement with the i2CAT Foundation to promote digital transformation in the social and socio-health sector	Catalonia	Regional	11/10/2024
12	SHINE destaca inovação e sustentabilidade com 3 projetos no 31º congresso da APDR [SHINE highlights innovation and sustainability with 3 projects at the 31st APDR congress]	Portugal	Regional	Not available

3.14 Scientific and conference publications

Participation of INTEGER consortium members in national and international scientific publications has been recognised as a crucial element for the visibility of the project within the scientific community.

A total of **5 scientific publications**, exceeding the proposed target of 2, have been produced (see Table 14), utilising platforms such as Zenodo, Springer Nature and journals like Slovenský Národopis and Sustainability (MDPI).

Table 14 - List of scientific and conference publications

	Title	Main author(s)	Format	Journal / Publisher / Link
1	Towards a more inclusive triple transition and quadruple helix innovation ecosystems: the case of the Catalonian Col·laboratori on Health and Wellbeing within the INTEGER project	A. Caro	Article	Slovenský národopis
2	Transformative Governance for the Future	A. Caro	Book	Springer Nature
3	Towards the Social Innovation Lighthouse	C. Dantas, A. Caro-González, M. Cabrita, N. Machado, W. v. Staalduinen, M. Machowska, A. Włodarczyk-Gebik, O. Vallejo	Article	Zenodo

4	INTEGER: Fostering social-business collaboration for impactful change	C. Dantas, I. Saavedra, N. Machado, J. Bernitt, R. Nualart	Conference article	Zenodo
5	Open our Innovation Ecosystems to All: the INTEGER Project Case Study	F. Canseco-López, A. Serra, M. Martorell	Article	Sustainability (MDPI)

To guarantee successful participation in these publications, the following guidelines have been shared with partners.

Authorship

Before starting any publication, collaborating investigators are encouraged to engage in discussions regarding authorship, ensuring all relevant members of INTEGER are involved. All co-authors must meet the following conditions:

1. Make substantial contributions to the conception and design, data acquisition, data analysis, and interpretation of results.
2. Participate in drafting the article or critically revising it for significant intellectual content.
3. Provide final approval for the version to be published.
4. Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work, ensuring any questions related to accuracy or integrity are properly addressed and resolved.

Acknowledgment of INTEGER Support

The following wording is recommended when acknowledging research carried out in whole or in part with INTEGER financial support: This document/paper is an output from the project INTEGER - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions. The INTEGER project is supported by the European Commission under HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions (Grant agreement ID: 101096563). The INTEGER project brings together a team from: i2CAT - Fundacio Privada i2CAT, Internet i Innovacio Digital a Catalunya (Spain), Universitat Rovira i Virgili | Fundació URV (Spain), F6S Innovation (Ireland), Behoerde fuer Arbeit, Gesundheit, Soziales, Familie und Integration Hamburg (Germany), Uniwersytet Jagiellonski (Poland), Krakow Technology Park (Poland), SHINE 2Europe, Lda (Portugal), and AFEdeMy, Academy on Age-Friendly Environments in Europe B.V. (The Netherlands).

3.15 Events, Conferences and other dissemination opportunities

Project partners actively participated in **40 relevant regional, national, and international conferences, events, and meetings**, where they communicated project activities and disseminated results through presentations, speaking engagements, and exhibition opportunities. A detailed list of these events can be found in Table 15.

At the beginning of the project, there was a focus on local meetings. However, after one year, efforts were made to refine communication and dissemination strategies, targeting broader audiences through diverse formats such as workshops, international conferences, and symposiums.

In total, this included the participation in **13 conferences or summits** held within the regional contexts of pilot regions (Catalonia, Hamburg, Krakow) and internationally, in locations such as Portugal (Porto, Leiria), Belgium (Brussels), and Kenya (Nairobi). Additionally, **19 meetings and workshops**, mainly organised by regional partners, showcased the INTEGER project or its achievements in the context of regional collaborations.

Moreover, partners participated in **8 other events**, both online and onsite in pilot regions, where they used the opportunity to disseminate information about INTEGER, further expanding the project's reach and impact.

Table 15 - Conferences, capacity building programmes and meetings

	Conference / capacity building programme / meetings	Main author(s)	Format
1	Co-creation session: business to business meeting. Barcelona, December 2022	i2CAT	Onsite (Barcelona, Spain)
2	Meeting with Vitalise Project. December 2022	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
3	Project presentation INTEGER at the working group for sustainable city health. Online. March 2023	HAM	Online
4	Meeting with Lifescience cluster members. March 2023.	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
5	Presenting INTEGER to a potential collaborator from the educational and civil society field (Pere Tarrés Foundation). March 2023.	i2CAT	Onsite (Barcelona, Spain)
6	Presenting INTEGER to a new Assistencial Robotic Lab (LabORA). March 2023.	i2CAT	Online
7	Interreg CE Smart Circuit Project Partner Meeting. Krakow. April 2023	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
8	Networking with the Hamburg health Kiosk and preparation of the presentation. Online. April, 2023	HAM	Online
9	SDG 48h Challenge within Social Innovations Demo Days. Jagiellonian University. June, 2023	UJ	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
10	Summer Jam 2023, Krakow. July 2023	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
11	Meeting with organisers of Lifescience Open Space conference. July 2023	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
12	Congress of Polish Social Policy. Warsaw. May 2023	UJ	Onsite (Warsaw, Poland)

13	Presentation at ISA Congress. Melbourne/online. June/July 2023	UJ	Online
14	NGO Event in Kraków. Better Krakow. July 2023	UJ	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
15	Meeting with Netmentora. July 2023	URV	Online
16	International Conference on Social Innovation Guimaraes. 6-8 Sept 2023 https://in3.dem.ist.utl.pt/events/isirc-2023/	i2CAT	Onsite (Guimarães, Portugal)
17	WHO Stakeholder Consultation Meeting. Krakow. March 2023	UJ	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
18	Open Living Lab Days. Barcelona. Sept 2023	i2CAT	Onsite (Barcelona, Spain)
19	21st European Week of Regions and Cities. Brussels. October, 2023	SHINE/AFE	Onsite (Brussels, Belgium)
20	Inner ministreal workshop in the Department of Health. Hamburg. December, 2023	HAM	Onsite (Hamburg, Germany)
21	Workshop with Hamburg stakeholders. Online. January, 2023.	HAM	Online
22	Meetings with stakeholders with extensive experience in health and wellness innovation. Online. July 2023 (Dates: 04/07/2023; 07/07/2023; 10/07/2023;10/07/2023; 14/07/2023; 20/07/2023;21/07/2023; 05/09/2023)	FURV	Online
23	Difusion & spreading. Introducing INTEGER to other local initiative that i2CAT leads. September 2023	i2CAT	Online
24	Meeting with the University of Applied Science Hamburg and the Veddel Polyclinic. December 2023	HAM	Online
25	Follow-up meeting after the AHathon, organised by Cluster Life Science Cracow. February 2024	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
26	Presentation of INTEGER in the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. March 2024	i2CAT	Onsite (Brussels, Belgium)
27	Presentation of INTEGER in MWC – GSMA. March 2024	i2CAT	Onsite (Barcelona, Spain)
28	Presentation of Col·laboratori Catalunya on Health & Wellbeing in Giga Day. March 2024.	i2CAT	Onsite (Barcelona, Spain)
29	International Conference Building Inclusive and Participatory Environments. May 2024.	i2CAT	Onsite (Porto, Portugal)
30	31st APDR Congress on Regional Innovation Ecosystems and Sustainable Development	SHINE	Onsite (Leiria, Portugal)

31	Meeting with the CEO of Health Device Start Up. July 2024.	FURV	Online
32	Project meeting for the Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries for Collaboration, Competitiveness, Sustainability, and Innovation. August 2024.	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
33	Hamburg Innovation Summit. September 2024.	i2CAT / HAM /KTP	Onsite (Hamburg, Germany)
34	41st IASP Conference. September 2024	KTP	Onsite (Nairobi)
35	Hafencity University Hamburg + Healthy City Generator Meeting. September 2024	i2CAT / HAM / KTP	Onsite (Hamburg, Germany)
36	Horizon Europe webinar on legal and financial aspects (INTEGER was shared as an example). October 2024	SHIENE	Online
37	Meeting with ISIHUB Poland. October 2024	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
38	WeMind International Forum. November 2024	i2CAT	Onsite (Barcelona, Spain)
39	Life Science Open Space Summit 2024. November 2024	KTP	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)
40	VII Congress of Silver Economy. December 2024	UJ	Onsite (Krakow, Poland)

Additionally, various events organised by project partners have played a significant role in disseminating the project. For example, the partners hosted a series of "Col-laborathons," including one general event and three regional ones. Furthermore, the active participation of project partners in coordination meetings of sister/brother projects, as well as in events held by existing networks, has provided valuable opportunities to exchange knowledge, learn, systematize information, and test the INTEGER 4H model. These activities have also allowed partners to refine, enrich, and disseminate the model while promoting its adoption and scalability across other regions and sectors. This effort was further supported by the Col-laber training, along with the training and incubation processes, which collectively strengthened the project's impact.

Figure 25 - Screenshot of the news about Col-laborathons featured on the INTEGER website.

3.16 Webinars

The INTEGER project aimed to bridge the significant gap between social innovators, entrepreneurs, and their regional innovation ecosystems, in order to fully leverage the potential of EU innovation, particularly in the critical area of healthy living. To engage a wide range of stakeholders, a series of **three exchange webinars** were planned to share insights and experiences from social innovation actors within innovation ecosystems.

The **first webinar** session was organised by i2CAT, with 39 participants, shortly after the project's inception. During this session, i2CAT demonstrated how a local social innovation ecosystem, such as the regional *Catalunya Col·laboratori de Salut i Benestar* (Health & Wellbeing), could grow, engage, and evolve into a European-scale initiative.

A **second webinar** (recording [here](#)) hosted by i2CAT for the Catalonian region, on February 8, 2024, furthering the exchange of knowledge and best practices explaining the Catalonia Col·laboratori and the grow of Digital Social Innovation through other sister projects such INTEGER. More details can be found on *Deliverable 4.2 – EU-wide INTEGER innovative community constituted* [5].

The **final webinar**, organised by SHINE, saw participation from 32 attendees representing Portugal, Greece, Lithuania, Romania, Norway, Italy, Germany, and Estonia. Several projects expressed collaborate with INTEGER on joint articles that were disseminated on LinkedIn articles, focusing on the similarities and differences between their initiatives. Additionally, all sister projects showed interest in sharing their presentations on the [INTEGER learning network](#). This event led to at least one follow-up meeting between two of the sister projects and to the promotion of INTEGER on their respective social media platforms. Further details about this event can be found in *Deliverable 5.2 – Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives*.

One notable highlight is that, as a result of this webinar, joint articles have been developed with other sister projects (as detailed in the section above “Articles”). Additionally, some participants joined the EU Col-laboratory by signing the Terms of Reference. This event proved to be an effective manner for disseminating the project and fostering collaborations.

Figure 26 – Third webinar screenshot

4. STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS & ENGAGEMENT PLAN

The INTEGER Consortium has built upon an initial stakeholder scoping exercise undertaken for the proposal, to develop a more definitive analysis of the project's key stakeholders who could have an interest in the activities and results of the INTEGER project and design a focused engagement strategy for them.

Identifying and defining this target audience, as well as a tailored engagement strategy, helped to ensure the effectiveness of dissemination activities and the full exploitation of results.

4.1 Stakeholder analysis

A preliminary analysis of the stakeholders has been performed leading to the identification of the following categories of actors, all represented in the consortium composition and/or in the groups of actors to be engaged, as described in *Deliverable 5.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders' Engagement Plan* [1].

Partners identified 33 stakeholders within each ecosystem - Krakow, Catalonia, and Hamburg - across national, regional, and local levels. Additionally, they recognised key international stakeholders vital to the project's success (see APPENDIX 1: Initial list of specific target stakeholders).

To define participants and organisations, **stakeholders were classified using the quadruple helix model**, which identifies four key areas of innovation within innovation ecosystems: Academia, Industry, Civil Society, and Government. Depending on the stakeholder type, they are affiliated with one of these four helixes. The operationalisation of these stakeholder types is detailed in the table below, which references the stakeholder categories outlined in *Deliverable 5.1* [1]:

Table 16 - Definition of stakeholder types categorised by helix

Helix	Stakeholder type	Definition
Academia	Universities	Higher education institutions that provide academic training, conduct research, and foster innovation while collaborating with public and private sectors to address societal challenges.
	Other research organisations	Institutions dedicated to advancing knowledge through scientific studies, innovation, and the dissemination of research findings, often collaborating with academia, industry, and governments.
Industry	Technology providers	Companies or organisations that develop, deliver, and maintain technological solutions, tools, or platforms for various applications.
	Business actors	Entrepreneurs, companies, or stakeholders involved in economic activities, contributing to market development and job creation.

Civil society	Citizens, NGOs and non-formal active groups	Individuals and community organisations advocating for change, supporting local initiatives, and contributing to societal progress through grassroots efforts.
	Social innovators	Individuals or organisations developing creative solutions to social problems, aiming to improve well-being and drive positive societal change.
Government	Regulatory bodies	Organisations responsible for creating and enforcing rules and standards to ensure compliance within specific industries or sectors.
	Public authorities	Governmental entities at various levels that manage public resources, deliver services, and ensure societal well-being.
	Policy-makers	Individuals or groups responsible for developing policies and strategies to address societal challenges and guide public and private actions.
	International networks	Cross-border alliances or coalitions fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and coordinated action among diverse stakeholders.

A total of **164** organisations participated in the **regional events**, while **118** were involved in the interregional events. Altogether, **254 unique organisations** engaged across both types of events (see Figure 27), including **93** from **industry** (88 business actors and 5 technology providers), **54** from **academia** (35 universities and 19 other research organisations), **50** from **government** (36 public authorities, 10 regulatory bodies, 2 policymakers, and 2 international networks), and **43** from **civil society** (23 citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups, and 20 social innovators), as well as **14** from **other sectors**.

Figure 27 – Number of organisations by helix involved in the activities conducted within the scope of regional and interregional events of the INTEGER project

Moreover, **125** organisations are from **Catalonia** (with an additional 3 from other parts of Spain), **54** from **Krakow** (with 4 more from other regions of Poland), **33** from **Hamburg** (plus 4 from other parts of Germany), **2** are **EU-wide**, **2** are **global**, **20** are from **other countries** (including Colombia, Turkey, Latvia, Portugal, Lithuania, Norway, Italy, Romania, and Estonia), and **7** are from unknown regions.

4.2 Stakeholder engagement

After determining the main stakeholders, the consortium identified them through their power, influence, and interest in what the project is developing. This analysis was essential to organise the interest of the stakeholders in the project and describe the engagement plan. The Power Interest Grid was developed to help with these stakeholders' segregation [6]. When

stakeholders are mapped on a power/interest grid, it is possible to determine who has high or low power to affect the project, and who has a high or low interest. The Power Interest Grid tool is divided by quadrants in a matrix, one side the power and on the other side the interest. It is necessary to identify if the stakeholder/s has/have high or low power and high or low interest. Depending on the place the actor is located, the actions that the project took have been different. An organisation with high power needs to be kept satisfied, so their opinions must be heard and implemented, while stakeholders with high interest need to be kept informed. If the organisation has both, it is necessary to manage its expectations very closely.

Based on the classification by helix and stakeholder type, a **Power-Interest Grid** [7] was developed to visualise stakeholders' capabilities, following *Deliverable 5.1* [1]. These grids help determine which stakeholders have the power to influence the project and which partners need to remain engaged. The Power-Interest Grid is a matrix with quadrants that visualise power on one axis and interest on the other. Organisations have been placed in the grid according to their stakeholder type, as shown in Figure 28 - Power-Interest Grid.

Figure 28 - Power-Interest Grid

This analysis was important for developing the initial engagement plan. Using this matrix, the project was able to identify and better understand the different strategies required to reach each type of stakeholder effectively. The full list of engaged organisations is available in APPENDIX 2: Power-Interest Grid for INTEGER Activities.

The stakeholder analysis and engagement strategy, presented in *Deliverable 5.1* [1], outlined the objectives for engaging with stakeholders - whether for communication, dissemination, or both. It also provided the specific rationale for engaging with each stakeholder group and clearly defined why INTEGER needs to communicate and disseminate its activities, benefits, and outcomes to its target audiences. While *Deliverable 4.4 - Report on Coordination Actions with Key Related Initiatives*) focused on stakeholder engagement during regional events, and

Deliverable 5.2 - Stakeholder Liaison with Relevant Initiatives emphasized interregional events, this deliverable aims to provide a broader perspective, covering both regional and interregional activities.

Out of the **254 organisations** involved in the project, **113** were classified as ***requiring close management***, including 88 business actors, 20 social innovators, and 5 technology providers (see Figure 29). These stakeholders played a key role in the project and were actively involved in a wide range of activities, including study visits, the initial diagnosis of challenges and needs, col-laborathons at both regional and interregional levels, the consultation process on the 4H Model, as well as other regional and interregional activities such as webinars, col-laber training, and the incubation process.

In addition, **48 organisations**, which included 36 public authorities, 10 regulatory bodies, and 2 policy-makers, were engaged to ***ensure their opinions were heard and implemented***. Their involvement primarily focused on the initial activities of diagnosing challenges and needs, as well as meetings such as the Key Stakeholder Meeting in Hamburg, Special Interest Groups in Krakow, and information sessions in Catalonia, alongside regional study visits.

Furthermore, **68 organisations requiring minimal monitoring** participated in activities due to their interest. This group included 35 universities, 19 research organisations, and 14 other stakeholders, who contributed to the consultation on the 4H Model and took part in col-laborathons at both regional and interregional levels and also in training activities. This group also showed significant enthusiasm for the project's activities, likely due to the strong connection between universities and research organisations and living labs, which closely aligned with the objectives of the INTEGER project.

Lastly, **25 organisations** were identified as stakeholders ***to be kept informed about the project's decisions***. Despite being the smallest group, it included 2 international networks invited to participate in training sessions as speakers, leveraging their expertise while offering them an opportunity to learn more about the project. Citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups were also engaged, mainly through study visits, with some taking part in col-laborathons as well.

Additionally, a total of **28 organisations participated in both regional and interregional events**. These included **2** organisations from **Hamburg** (Help Mee Schmerztherapie GmbH and Philips, both from the industry as business actors), **1** from **Krakow** (Cluster LifeScience Kraków, classified as civil society, specifically a social innovator), and **25** from **Catalonia**. Of the Catalan participants, 11 represented industry (business actors), 5 were from government (4 public authorities and 1 regulatory body), 4 were civil society organisations, and 5 were academic institutions, specifically research organisations. The organisations from Catalonia included Bax & Company, Conorex Consulting, CSA, DoS, Memima Baby, Consorci Sanitari de Terrassa, EureCat Hub FoodTech, Fundació iSocial, Fundació Pere Tarrés, Fundació Salut Empordà, Giromed Institute, Hospital Sant Joan de Déu, Hub d'Innovació Social i Sanitària – HiSS, ICS, Ideas for Change, IDIAP JGol/ICS, IVL Consulting, Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa, Neapolis, Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili, SeniorLab, Valls Genera, WeMindCluster, Suara Cooperativa, and Ship2B.

Figure 29 – Power-Interest Grid for regional and interregional activities

5. VOICES OF STAKEHOLDERS: SUCCESS AND IMPACT

Feedback on the impact of the INTEGER project was collected from a total of 24 stakeholders through two methods: interviews and surveys. Five stakeholders were interviewed, with a focus on their experiences during the mentoring sessions, while 19 stakeholders participated in surveys, providing feedback on the overall development and implementation of the INTEGER project.

5.1 SUCESS STORIES

The INTEGER project's initiatives have had a profound impact on stakeholders across various sectors. This impact is best illustrated through the testimonials and feedback from participants who participated in the mentorship sessions in each pilot region.

Stakeholders emphasised the importance of **skills development and strategic support** provided during the mentorship sessions. As Karina Simieli (SeniorLab, Catalonia) noted *"The mentor offered us valuable insights, a fresh view about the project for discovering new possibilities around the value proposition. Being part of the mentoring process also helped us to stay focused and on track"*. Similarly, Marta Rofin (Bax & Company, Catalonia) reflected on the mentorship's transformative impact, explaining how it helped her startup gain *"clarity on the strategic alignment of different workstreams and understanding their interrelations"*. She further added that, *"The mentorship helped us approach the internal structure of our startup more professionally, integrating a comprehensive business and team vision."* Additionally, she highlighted the shift in mindset, stating, *"It taught us to embrace the role of a business leader rather than solely focusing on technical aspects, which was transformative for making strategic decisions and driving long-term growth"*.

Participants also benefited from external perspectives on **market opportunities and implementation strategies**. Monika Bartkowicz (Drogowskazy, Krakow) remarked, *"The mentorship gave us an external perspective, drawing attention to inconsistencies, estimating market opportunities, and identifying areas for implementation and new perspectives. It highlighted the challenges we face and provided valuable tips for developing a sustainable product"*.

Mentorship also played an important role in **empowering participants to take ownership of their decisions**. Natalia Bialobrzewska (Kontakt Kollektiv, Hamburg) shared, *"Sometimes entrepreneurs just need the right questions asked to help them reflect on their next steps, rather than receiving direct solutions. It's about finding a balance where the mentee feels empowered to make decisions"*.

For some stakeholders, INTEGER's mentorship significantly **enhanced business planning and increased visibility**. Albert Munne (Memima, Catalonia) shared how INTEGER *"gave us an opportunity to grow"*. He also mentioned it helped refine their business planning and market approach, aligning their focus and priorities, while also increasing the visibility of their initiative.

The mentorship sessions also highlighted the importance of **collaborative progress**. Rosina Malagrida (IrsiCaixa Living Lab for Health, Catalonia) expressed her gratitude, saying, *"In just five*

hours, we made significant progress. We have come a long way, and while there is still more to do, we are grateful for the support and excited to explore further collaborations”.

5.2 PERSPECTIVES ON INTEGER DEVELOPMENT AND IMPACT

As part of the INTEGER project's final phase, a **stakeholder survey** was conducted to collect insights from key participants across the pilot regions. The survey aimed to evaluate the project's impact, identify challenges, and gather recommendations for sustaining and expanding its outcomes.

The questionnaire was **distributed via email by i2CAT**, targeting stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and civil society. A total of **19 responses** were collected from representatives of various sectors and regions.

Figure 30 – Screenshot of impact assessment survey on the INTEGER project

Socio demographic profile of respondents

Age distribution

The majority of survey participants belonged to Generation Y (63%) followed by Generation X. No responses were recorded from the from Baby Boomer or Generation Z groups.

Figure 31 - Age distribution of survey respondents

Gender representation

Women represented the majority of respondents, accounting for nearly 70% of the total.

Figure 32 – Gender representation of survey respondents

Regional distribution

Regarding regional representation, **Catalonia** accounted for **36.8%** of respondents, followed by **Krakow (31.6%)** and **Hamburg (21.1%)**. A small number of responses also came from **Portugal**, though the specific regions were not indicated, with **Porto** being mentioned separately.

Figure 33 – Regional distribution of survey respondents

Educational background

Most participants hold a Ph.D., followed by those with a master's degree, high school diploma, and bachelor's degree, while Ph.D. students represented the smallest percentage.

Figure 34 – Educational background of survey respondents

Influence on stakeholder interaction

All respondents (100%) reported that INTEGER significantly improved communication and collaboration with external actors. Half of the participants (50%) noted an increase in the project's visibility, while a slightly higher percentage (55%) stated that their understanding of European initiatives and key ecosystem stakeholders deepened. A smaller portion (10%) indicated that INTEGER facilitated access to new resources or funding opportunities, whereas a few respondents (5%) mentioned that the project had little impact on their external engagement.

Regarding the external factors that influenced engagement, collaboration with public institutions was the most significant, cited by nearly half of respondents (45%), followed by the growing demand for digital services (35%). Some participants (15%) highlighted the integration of new technologies and business models, while others (5%) referenced regulatory and legislative changes. These insights reinforce the importance of institutional support and digital transformation trends in fostering sustainable innovation.

Impact on collaboration and organisational management

The project enhanced the **culture of innovation and internal collaboration**, as reported by 73% of respondents. **Internal strategy aimed at digital innovation** comes next, mentioned by 26% of respondents. **Adaptability and digital training of staff** is also a key consideration, noted by 26% of the answers. Other factors like **technological infrastructure** and **awareness of DSI** are mentioned less frequently but still play a role in fostering a successful digital transformation.

Figure 39 - Graph of respondents' answers to "Which of these elements, from an internal perspective, have been influenced by the project?"

The majority of responses (36%) indicate that the project **had little or no impact on internal management**. **Improved coordination between teams** was the second most cited impact, with 31% of participants mentioning it. Additionally, **efficiency and agility in internal processes** were seen as improved by 26% of respondents, and only a small percentage (5%) noted that the **complexity of internal management** had increased

How do you think the project has influenced internal and organizational management?

19 responses

Figure 40 - Graph of respondents' answers to "How do you think the project has influenced internal and organisational management?"

Innovation, collaboration and economic impact

The majority of responses (63%) indicate that the project **had a moderate impact on the ability to innovate**. A significant portion (26%) feel that it **considerably increased the ability to innovate and implement new ideas**, while a small percentage (15%) stated that it **had no noticeable impact on innovation**.

What impact has the project had on your capacity for social innovation?

19 responses

Figure 41 - Graph of respondents' answers to "What impact has the project had on your capacity for social innovation?"

Key visible improvements included **increased interaction and collaboration with social actors (58%)**, greater ability to manage innovative projects (37%), and improved efficiency and

productivity (15%). Changes in communication with end users were also highlighted as an area of improvement.

What kind of visible changes or improvements have you noticed as a result of the project?

19 responses

Figure 42 - Graph of respondents' answers to "What kind of visible changes or improvements have you noticed as a result of the project?"

In terms of **economic impact**, 52% of respondents identified the emergence of **new ideas with the potential to develop into future enterprises** as the most frequent outcome. Other impacts included improved networks and competition (26%) and the creation of social entrepreneurial projects (15%).

Do you think there has been any kind of economic impact in your environment?

19 responses

Figure 43 - Graph of respondents' answers to "Do you think there has been any kind of economic impact in your environment?"

Values and potential of the INTEGER4H network

According to respondents, the core values of **INTEGER4H** revolve around **open communication, cooperation, and teamwork** across sectors and geographical regions. The project prioritizes **integration, knowledge sharing, and innovation** to tackle cross-cutting challenges effectively. Key principles include **mutual understanding, sustainability**, and fostering **long-term impact**. Additionally, the initiative places significant emphasis on **openness, community engagement**, and **bridging the gap between business-oriented and socially driven enterprises**.

The INTEGER4H network facilitated collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including businesses, public administrations, and investors. Respondents noted its role in promoting partnerships, expanding initiatives to new regions, and connecting social and digital processes to address challenges in sectors such as **education, health, and the environment**. Several participants emphasized the need for follow-up actions to maintain momentum and achieve lasting cultural change. The network was also recognized for supporting funding opportunities and advancing sustainable development through **cross-sectoral cooperation**.

Transfer of knowledge and collaboration

Collaboration and knowledge exchange were promoted through various activities, including **meetings, workshops, training sessions, seminars, and mentoring programs**. Regional collaboration between **Hamburg, Krakow, and Catalonia** was frequently highlighted, as well as the importance of **interregional cooperation** through key events such as **Col-laborathons and Model Sessions**. Although most events were well-organised, some participants identified the need for more **structured and formal collaboration frameworks** to enhance consistency and long-term partnerships.

Knowledge sharing was one of the most frequently cited benefits for other external actors (30%), followed by mutual learning and joint innovation (27%), increased awareness of other institutions (18%), improved collaboration among organisations and social actors (14%), promoted the creation of digital collaboration networks (7%) and improved the ability to implement digital solutions in other entities (4%).

80% of the respondents said that Col-laler role is important to support and guide social innovation processes.

Let us know your thoughts about the Facilitator or Col-laber Role.
 19 responses

Figure 44 - Graph of respondents' answers to "Let us know your thoughts about the Facilitator or Col-laber role"

Sustainability and future perspective

The project contributed significantly to territorial sustainability, with 60% of respondents reporting increased project resilience and adaptability. Improvements in the ability to generate sustainable financing and resources were cited by 15%, although 25% of participants felt that INTEGER had not significantly impacted sustainability in their regions.

Looking ahead, 73% of respondents identified **public-private partnerships** as essential to ensuring the sustainability of digital transformation efforts. Continuous **staff training** (68%), promoting digital social innovation (52%), integrating new funding mechanisms (47%), and supporting European social entrepreneurship (42%) were also considered critical.

Figure 45 - Graph of respondents' answers to "What factors do you consider essential to guarantee the sustainability of digital transformation in the future?"

INTEGER4H was viewed as highly replicable and scalable, provided it is adapted to local contexts. Participants emphasized the importance of understanding local needs, fostering cross-sector partnerships, and providing tailored training in key areas such as **digital inclusion** (digital literacy), **environmental sustainability** (environmental protection, community development, and the promotion of sustainable practices), and **education** (promoting self-determined ageing, social inclusion, and skill development).

Challenges and objectives

Participants identified several challenges, including **limited financial resources**, resistance to change, and difficulties in digital skill development. Technological and infrastructure limitations, as well as challenges in transferring approaches between regions, were also highlighted.

Despite these challenges, participants recognised several strengths within the project, such as the **existing network (63%)** and the creation of **sessions for knowledge exchange (63%)**. Other factors like work on challenges and missions, European Network of Living Labs, and leadership from INTEGER partners were mentioned less frequently, but still contribute to the project's perceived success.

What are the main POTENTIALS that you have identified within the project?

19 responses

Figure 46 - Graph of respondents' answers to "What are the main potentials that you have identified within the project?"

Moving forward, key objectives for further digital transformation include enhancing collaboration with other projects (73%), developing new funding methods (63%), and providing additional training in digital skills (36%).

What objectives do you consider to be priority in order to continue progressing in the digital transformation of the project?

19 responses

Figure 47 - Graph of respondents' answers to "What objectives do you consider to be priority in order to continue progressing in the digital transformation of the project?"

Main conclusions

The survey results demonstrate INTEGER4H's significant contribution to fostering **digital social innovation** by promoting collaboration among academic institutions, public administrations, and social enterprises across regions. The project shifted perceptions of DSI from being **business-driven** to a more **inclusive and socially collaborative model**, highlighting its role in integrating **technology, social needs, and policy implementation**.

Participants gained valuable insights into funding strategies, professional networks, and sustainable digital practices. However, areas for improvement include **better public sector involvement, strategic planning, and communication tailored to local contexts**. Maintaining financial sustainability beyond public funding remains a key challenge.

By addressing these challenges and leveraging its core strengths, INTEGER4H is well-positioned for **replication and scalability** across various sectors, ensuring its long-term impact on **digital inclusion, environmental sustainability, and education**.

6. CONCLUSION AND LESSONS LEARNED

The INTEGER project's communication, dissemination, and engagement strategies were essential to its success, fostering a strong visual identity, increasing stakeholder participation, and ensuring the broad dissemination of project outcomes. These efforts were supported by the development of various materials, including 27 videos, 15 interviews, 6 newsletters, 23 infographics and visuals, 6 Zoom-specific issues, 12 press articles, and 5 scientific publications. The project's website attracted over 31,738 unique visitors. Social media, particularly LinkedIn, played a pivotal role in engagement, with its 441 followers significantly expanding INTEGER's visibility and reach. This impact was reflected in the publication strategy, with 7 out of the 8 articles being published on LinkedIn to maximize their outreach and engagement.

Participation in 40 events, meetings, and conferences significantly increased INTEGER's visibility. These, along with other INTEGER-led events, were supported by existing partner networks, such as NET4Age-Friendly, Investment Bank Hamburg, SHAFE Thematic Network, ENOLL-European Network of Living Labs, the European School of Social Innovation, among others detailed in Deliverable 5.1 [1].

A total of 254 unique organisations engaged with the project, including academia (54), industry (93), civil society (43), and government (50). Catalonia led participation with 125 organisations, followed by Krakow (54) and Hamburg (33). Engagement extended beyond the pilot regions, with 20 organisations from other countries, 2 EU-wide, 2 global, and 7 from unspecified locations. Catalonia's strong involvement reflected its early participation in the Col-laboratori initiative, whereas Krakow and Hamburg's lower numbers highlighted the need for targeted outreach. However, in Krakow, institutions were the most active participants in regional events, demonstrating a stronger engagement at the institutional level. The presence of 28 organisations in both regional and interregional events demonstrates the importance of adapting messaging to clearly highlight the benefits of interregional collaboration for stakeholders.

While industry had the highest participation, its engagement was less consistent compared to civil society in regional events, which responded more actively to INTEGER's focus on social innovation. Business stakeholders, often influenced by economic constraints, require a clearer value proposition to justify their involvement.

Key initiatives such as Col-laborathons, training sessions, mentoring, and incubation programmes provided valuable support on business model development, Social Return on Investment, and social innovation. While these sessions benefited from contributions by external experts, participant feedback highlighted the need for more hands-on exercises and additional time for platform registration, which could have strengthened engagement beyond the events.

The survey and interview feedback revealed that INTEGER successfully shifted perceptions of Digital Social Innovation, transforming it from a primarily business-driven approach to a more inclusive and socially collaborative model. Participants also noted that the mentorship sessions were particularly valuable, providing significant benefits to those who took part. Additionally, participants highlighted the strong replication potential and scalability of several INTEGER activities and the Quadruple Helix (4H) Model, which was recognised as a very positive outcome.

7. FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

The project's strong focus on collaboration, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement has led to impactful outcomes such as the Col-laborathons, which can be replicated in other regions. Additionally, the 4H Model and the Col-laber profile offer opportunities for testing and application by experts across the quadruple helix.

To ensure the continuity and expansion of the EU Col-laboratory, the consortium remains committed to quarterly meetings and the use of the Decidim platform, which is expected to enhance stakeholder interaction by providing a more intuitive and sustainable solution.

Interregional collaboration can be strengthened through tailored messaging and targeted communication strategies that effectively highlight the benefits of engagement. It is crucial to refine sector-specific communication to better address the distinct needs of each quadruple helix stakeholder group. This includes adapting invitations and outreach materials to ensure more balanced participation across sectors. Given the varying availability and preferences of different organisations, offering flexibility in event format (onsite, online, hybrid) and duration may further support engagement.

The INTEGER project and its outcomes will be showcased in February 2025 at the [3rd Edition of Barcelona Health Innovation Week](#). This event aims to keep the project's results alive and promote their transfer and application across various stakeholders.

By leveraging existing networks, refining outreach efforts, and strengthening digital engagement, the project's legacy expects to continue to foster cross-sector innovation, interregional collaboration, and long-term impact across Europe.

REFERENCES

- [1] "D5.1 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND STAKEHOLDERS' ENGAGEMENT PLAN.pdf," Google Docs. Accessed: Jan. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-FPFFv5HAR1oBm9MgWj8AuRQzU2Thmk7/view?usp=embed_facebook
- [2] X. E. Barandiaran, A. Calleja-López, A. Monterde, and C. Romero, *Decidim, a Technopolitical Network for Participatory Democracy: Philosophy, Practice and Autonomy of a Collective Platform in the Age of Digital Intelligence*. in SpringerBriefs in Political Science. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-50784-7.
- [3] "D3.1 Comprehensive plan for capacity building activities and training pills delivery (I).pdf," Google Docs. Accessed: Jan. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1vMQrm8uFf3XIBRPgPn0ErOTvWAEqQKES/view?usp=embed_facebook
- [4] "D3.2-Comprehensive-plan-for-capacity-building-activities-and-training-pills-delivery-II.pdf." Accessed: Jan. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://integercollab.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/D3.2-Comprehensive-plan-for-capacity-building-activities-and-training-pills-delivery-II.pdf>
- [5] "D4.2---EU-wide-INTEGER-innovative-community-constituted.pdf." Accessed: Jan. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://integercollab.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/D4.2-%E2%80%93-EU-wide-INTEGER-innovative-community-constituted.pdf>
- [6] "Stakeholder Analysis - Winning Support for Your Projects." Accessed: Jan. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mindtools.com/aol0rms/stakeholder-analysis>
- [7] "ProjectManagement.com - Stakeholder Analysis using the Power Interest Grid." Accessed: Jan. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.projectmanagement.com/wikis/368897/Stakeholder-Analysis--using-the-Power-Interest-Grid>

APPENDIX 1: Initial list of specific target stakeholders

The Consortium has compiled an initial list of specific target stakeholders within the categories defined in the Stakeholder analysis, and these are presented below. Each regional partner team was responsible for preparing a comprehensive stakeholders' map, starting with key stakeholders to participate in the first actions of the project.

The list was compiled through a mix of desk research and partner feedback and provided a starting point as the project commences for targeted communication. It was reviewed and adapted as the project progressed. The emails are kept internally for reasons of data protection.

Table 12 - initial list of specific target stakeholders³

Cracow		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	National	The Polish Ministry of Health
	Regional	Marshall Office of Malopolska Region
	Local	Municipality Centre of Social Assistance
Civic Society	National	Polish National Initiative for Collaboration of Senior Councils
	Regional	Krakow Smog Alert
	Local	Senior Activity Centres
Industry	National	Polish Confederation Lewiatan
	Regional	Klaster Lifescience
	Local	DIABMED
Academia	National	Polish National Gerontological Association
	Regional	University of Science and technology Krakow
	Local	Faber Education Centre

³ This list is just a sample of key stakeholders, none of the cases are exhaustive lists.

Hamburg		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs
		Hamburg Ministry of Economy
		Hamburg Ministry of Science
Civic Society	Regional	Max und Ingeborg Herz Stiftung (Foundation)
		Patriotische Gesellschaft (Philantropic civil society organisation)
Industry	National	Aidhere
		Philips
	Regional	Health Innovation Port
Academia	Regional	University Hospital Hamburg
		University Hamburg
		Hamburg University of Applied Science
Other	Regional	Hamburg Investment Bank
		Cluster Agency Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH
4helix	Regional	Arbeitskreis nachhaltige Stadtgesundheit (transdisciplinary working group, Civil Society, Academia, Government, Economy)
Catalonia		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Type of Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Health department - Catalanian government

		Social & Family Department - Catalanian government
		Labour & Digital Society Department- Catalanian government
Civic Society	Local	Patient Associations
		Consell Català de la gent gran
		Association of "AMPA" Mothers and fathers of primary schools
		Neighbourhood associations
Industry	Regional	Giromed Institute
		Me Mima Baby
	National	Bax & Company
		Eurecat
Academia	Regional	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
		Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)
		Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
		Universitat Barcelona (UB)
International Stakeholders		
4 H areas		Type of Stakeholder
Government		DG Employment & Social inclusion
Civic Society		Age platform Europe
Industry		European Business & innovation Network

	Phillips Health innovation port ; Gaia AG
Academia	UNA Europa
	NET4Age COST action

APPENDIX 2: Power-Interest Grid for INTEGER activities

Hear their opinions and implement them

Public authorities

ACCIO - GENERALITAT DE CATALUNYA
Ajuntament de Viladecans (CAT)
Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú (CAT)
Althaia Xarxa Assistencial Universitària de Manresa
Catalan Ministry of health Government of Catalonia (CAT)
City of Dobczyce
City of Krakow Office
Conselh Generau d'Aran
Consorti Sanitari de Terrassa (CAT)
District Pharmaceutical Chamber
Fundació Salut Empordà. Hosp Figueres (CAT)
Generalitat de Catalunya
Hamburg Ministry of Economics
Hamburg Ministry of Urban Planning and Housing
Hamburgische Investitions- und Förderbank Hamburg (HAM)
Hospital Sant Joan de Deu (CAT)
Hospital Universitari Parc Tauli (CAT)
Igalada city council
Kraków City's center of Social Assistance
Małopolska Regional Development Agency UMWM (KRA)
Małopolska Regional Government Office
Marshall Office of Malopolska Region
Mataró city council
Ministry of cultural affairs
Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration (HAM)
National Chamber of Nursing Homes
Puigcerdà City Council
Regional Center for Social Policy (ROPS) in Krakow
Reus city council
Secretary of telecommunications and digital transformation government of Catalonia (CAT)
TIC Salut Social
Tremp city council
Valls Genera (CAT)
VHIR (CAT)
Vic city council
Vilanova i la Geltrú city council

Policy-makers

IDIBGI

Mutua M. Serveis Sanitaris, mutualisme i atencio a la dependencia

Regulatory bodies

ADRINOC
ASCASUD
ASPCAT
Consell Esportiu Baix Llobregat
Consorti de Salut social de Catalunya
Diputació de Tarragona
EureCat Hub FoodTEch
Health Public Agency of Catalonia
ICS Tarragona
Life Science Nord

Manage closely

Business actors

3 PG
4DHealth
ACG Coaching & Consulting
Ada Navarro (CAT)
AFEdemy (NL)
AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster (CAT)
Aufbruch.Hamburg (HAM)
Autoemployed
autònoma
Baltic Innovation Agency (EE)
Bax & Company. Healthy Cities (CAT)
Bee2be.tech
Beyond Emotion
Biwel
BizMarketing
BWI HH (HAM)
CENFIM/AMBIT/HABITAT
CINGI
Clúster TIC Sud
Connecting Dots (LT)
Conorex Consulting (CAT)
Control live
Cracow. Instytut Wspomagania Wychowania (KRA)
Csa
Cuideo
D4KAI Consultoria

Didactiba
DoS
eHealthAI
Eoh-for-Good (SP)
EPAM System (Poland)
EpiGuard (NO)
excagol medtech
F6S (UK)
Farmabol
Find Air
Fondazione David Chiossone
Fonduri Structurale (RO)
Fractalogy.eu
Free-lance
Fundació Èpica Fura dels Baus (CAT)
Fundacja Internationaler Bund Polska (KRA)
Giromed Institute (CAT)
GLJ
GlucoFit
GoodGut
Help Mee Schmerztherapie GmbH (HAM)
Hub4industry
ICS
IFB Hamburg (GER)
IGNITE Serious play
Innopro Consulting
IVL Consulting (CAT)
Josep Comas
Krakow Technology Park (KRA)
Lithuanian Innovation Centre (LT)
Memima baby (CAT)
Mire Mat
MJN Neuroserveis
MSM Assessoria i Innovació en Salut, SL
Neapolis
Never Average
Noupunt
Octavi Roig - D4Ki Consultoria
OnaLabs
Optimedis
Parenting Technologies
PatientZero Games
Philips (GER)
Prawnik (KRA)

Project AHEAD (IT)
QR codes
Qualitas Social Tech (CAT)
Saluscoop
SHINE (PT)
Ship2B (CAT)
Social Innovation Lab at Grünhof (GE)
Som essència sonora
Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (GER)
Suara Cooperativa (CAT)
Talent Passport
TicSud
Trentino Social Tank (IT)
t-valley ecosystem (CAT)
VAC-15
Waterologies
YASYT Tech & Knowledge
YourY Network (Global)

Technology providers

Aragonese Institute of Health Sciences (SP)
B&W MED
Comarch Healthcare
LEITAT Technological Center (CAT)
Warmie

Social innovators

Asociació tarragona intercultural
Care City Lab
Citolab Cornellà
Cluster LifeScience Kraków
Eugènia Juhé
Foundation Internationaler Bund Polska
Foundation Supporting Education Archezja
Fundació AEMA
Fundació Viver de Bell-lloc
Fundación Épica La Fura dels Baus
Gesundheit.Lokal
Gesundheitszentrum Mümmelmannsberg
InmoDelta - Ajuntament de Viladecans
Invest Billstedt / Horn
Lohbrügger Gesundheitszentrum Harburg Mümmelmannsberg
Lokales Gesundheitszentrum Harburg

Merkury
Origen Salut Integrativa
Poliklinik Veddel
Xarxa Omnia

Monitor with a minimum effort**Universities**

Aalborg University (Denmark)
Abdullah Gül University and Wellbeing Association (Turkey)
Center of Technology Transfer Jagiellonian University
Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics -CED- (CAT)
Economic University
EKA University of Applied Sciences (Latvia)
FCT NOVA - UCIBIO and Humanized Solutions (PT)
Fundació Universitària del Bages (CAT)
Hafen City University
Hamburg University of Applied Science
Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (Turkey)
IBCH PAS (KRA)
Ignatianum University in Krakow
Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry Polish Academy of Sciences (Poland)
Jagiellonian University (KRA)
Living Lab Universidad de la Sabana (Colombia)
Medicial University of Lodz (PL)
Norwegian University of Science and Technology
SWPS University (Warsaw, PL)
the Agriculture University
ThessAHALL
Tischner European Univeristy
UAB
UAB Core Salut Mental
Universitat Central de Catalunya Universitat de Manresa
Universitat Central de Catalunya Universitat de Vic UVic-UCC LISD
Universitat de Girona UdG
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (CAT)
Universitat Rovira i Virgili URV (CAT)
University Bremen
University Hospital Hamburg Eppendorf
University of Siegen
UOC
Valencian Iternational University (SP)
Warsaw University of Life Sciences (Warsaw, PL)

Other research organisations

Barcelona Health Hub (CAT)
CEI Torrefarrera
CSMC Cluster Salut Mental Catalunya (CAT)
Diagnostyka
Fundació Sant Hospital (CAT)
Hub d'innovació social i sanitària - HiSS (CAT)
i2CAT (CAT)
IDIAP JGoI / ICS
Institut Català d'Investigació Química
Institut de Robòtica per la Dependència
Instituto Robotica (CAT)
ISGlobal
IT
L'ITA Associació d'Antropologia
Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (CAT)
Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili (CAT)
Sano - Centre for Computational Medicine (Krakow, PL)
Social Innovation Exchange (Global)
WeMind Cluster (CAT)

Other

ATOMÓWKI Team
Balicka Team
Chłopcy WIMIRowcy Team
Edisonda Team
FGGH IP
Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH
Haamburg Investment Bank
IGWA Team
IKS Team
Lecostar Team
Life Sience Hamburg GmbH
RESIST Project
SILVERSPARKS Team
Working Group of Sustainable City Health

Keep informed about what the project has decided

International networks

ENOLL European Network of Living Labs (EU)
ESSI. European School of Social Innovation (EU)

Citizens, NGOs and non-formal active groups

Albert Social Cooperative
Associació La Teulada
Association of Social Innovators
Civel Society
Edki
FRDL MISTiA
Fundacio iSocial (CAT)
Fundació Pere Tarrés (CAT)
Fundació Visible (CAT)
Fundacja Brata Alberta (KRA)
Gruenhof e.V. (Germany)
ideas for Change (CAT)
Kollektiva (EL)
L'alzina (CAT)
Lithuanian Social Business Association (LISBA) (LT)
Marta
Mein Lido Foundation
Municipal Daily Social Welfare Home, Seniors' Club
Norway Health Tech (NO)
RDL Kraków
Sargim Foundation (before AEMA Foundation) (CAT)
SeniorLab (CAT)
ITA - Institut Català d'Antropologia (CAT)